

BARANGAY OFFICIALS' INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATIONS TECHNOLOGY COMPETENCIES TOWARD DIGITALIZATION: INPUTS FOR TRAINING PROGRAM

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ABSTRACT

This study evaluated the information and communication technology (ICT) skills of barangay officials within the local government unit (LGU) of Prosperidad, Agusan del Sur, using the National ICT Competency Standards (NICS-Basic) framework. A quantitative survey was conducted to assess competencies in six key areas: ICT Basics, Word Processing, Spreadsheets, Presentations, Information and Communication, and Computer Ethics and Security. Using Cochran's Formula for sample size determination, 155 participants were identified, utilizing cluster sampling based on barangay population size. Frequency and percentage were used to describe the demographic profile of the participants; mean score to determine the level of competencies; and test concerning means was used to determine the significant differences when grouped according to their demographic profile. The findings revealed that participants only possess basic competency levels across all six assessed areas, with significant differences in ICT skills based on age, gender, educational attainment, and position. A critical challenge identified was the lack of training relevant to ICT. Based on these findings, the study recommends that LGU-Prosperidad should prioritize an ICT training program covering all the skill sets in the NICS-Basic framework, tailored to address the diverse skills and demographics of barangay officials.

Keywords: *Barangay Officials, ICT Skills, ICT Training, National ICT Competency Standards (NICS-Basic)*

INTRODUCTION

Information and Communications Technology (ICT) has become an umbrella term for digitalization or digital communication. UNESCO defined ICT as a diverse set of technological tools and resources used to transmit, store, create, share or exchange information in technological tools such as computers, internet, telephony, and broadcasting technologies (UNESCO, n.d.). The European Union (EU) Directorate-General for Education and Culture also defined ICT competency as the confident and critical use of electronic media for work, leisure and communication. These competencies are related to logical and critical thinking, to high-level information management skills, and to well-developed communication skills (European Commission, 2004). In the field of public sector management, ICT will provide practical government services, increase government accountability to citizen's transparency, and promote more effective and efficient administration (The Scientific World, 2020). To harness the full potential of ICT nowadays and to use it as an advantage to an organization, one should assess the level of competencies among its workers and determine the gaps to successfully utilize ICT tools for development.

The development of ICT has dramatically reshaped the world of work. It undeniably highlighted occupations that are geared towards more intensive use of ICT, data analytics, and high value-adding social skills. With this demand, more than half of Filipino workers or 62% of the country's working population are using mostly general skills like service or clerical that are not attuned to the modern technology-driven world (Bayudan & Dacuycuy, 2021). With the fast-paced growth of technology, it is essential that the services among public and private sectors should also be aligned to this. The adoption of technology in both sectors, especially in developing countries is challenging though it is the most efficient way to provide services with accountability, transparency, and efficiency (Samsor, 2020). In education, teachers only showed basic competency in technology operation such as in understanding and the effective use of the internet and network applications and resources, demonstrating knowledge and skills in information and data management, basic troubleshooting, and limited knowledge in advanced applications (Batan et al, 2022 & Bayucca, 2021), while on the ICT usage among barangay officials, it was found that in using ICT, the slow network performance, individual's economic standing, and the fear in ICT usage were recorded as the constraints (Santiago et al, 2021). Further, AHDO (2022) recognizes that there is a need for a skill assessment of its workers to get ahead in the post-pandemic world.

In the context of the local government units (LGUs) in the Philippines, maximizing the use of ICT tools will elevate the kind of services they can offer to the community, as it will also enable public trust if the LGUs are doing effective ways of communication using the different platforms available (Flores & Asuncion, 2020). Hence, it is not just the educators who are challenged to adopt the use of technology especially in the changing form of the educational landscape where the use of ICT is essential, but also the LGUs. Thus, according to Batan et al (2021) and Santiago et al (2021) to bridge the gap between the ICT competencies and skills in delivering services it was suggested that a training program must be provided.

The emergence of digital technologies has profoundly affected and transformed almost every aspect of societal relations. These impacts have also reached public administration, including its governance. Digital technologies' rise has paved the way for the surfacing of a new public governance model called the Digital Era Governance (DEG) model (often referred to as e-government, digital government, e-governance, or digital governance) in which digital technologies play a central role (Ravšelj et al, 2022). It has been defined that digitalization is the adoption of digitized data and tools and can improve state capacity by making systems more simple, transparent and, thus, more efficient. (World Bank Group, 2021).

The Philippines is gearing towards “One Digitized Government”, where the use of ICT in government is seen to be an enabler to achieve digital transformation in the delivery of basic services. Through the Department of Information and Communications Technology (DICT), launched the E-Government Masterplan (eGMP) 2022 – an indicator that the country has been taking significant steps in adapting digital transformation to fuel and empower nation-building (DICT, 2019). Thus, to meet the goals of the national government, one should empower the people working with them.

The barangays, as the basic political unit in the Philippines, are expected to perform efficiently including the utilization of ICT (Santiago et al, 2021), as they serve as the primary planning and implementing unit of government policies, plans, programs, projects, and activities in the community (Chapter 1, Book III, Local Government Code of the Philippines). Hence, nowadays, to effectively cascade the information and facilitate the delivery of services to the community, the use of ICT tools is advantageous.

Prosperidad, being the capital of Agusan del Sur plays a vital role in the governance and development of the province. Examining the ICT competencies of the municipality of its barangay officials is essential for the successful implementation of digital initiatives that align with the national agenda for digital transformation. Moreover, it is noticeable that there is a gap in finding literature regarding the ICT competencies of barangay officials, particularly in Prosperidad. This study aims to fill the gap by providing valuable insights to the local government about the current state of ICT competencies among local chief executives, barangay officials, and appointive officials of LGU-Prosperidad across the municipality's 32 barangays.

By doing so, the study provides a foundational framework for the local government unit of Prosperidad to effectively plan and implement a comprehensive ICT training program. It will facilitate the strategic allocation of resources to address the identified needs and support policy-making decisions, particularly those related to digitized transactions. Furthermore, the study aims to empower local authorities with the confidence and skills to effectively use ICT tools, thereby enhancing their capacity to deliver quality services to the community. Generally, Prosperidad is not only an ideal area of study but also a vital starting point in the province of Agusan del Sur for fostering digital competency that can drive provincial progress.

Research Questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the participants in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age;
 - 1.2 Gender;
 - 1.3 Highest Educational Attainment;
 - 1.4 Number of years in Service;
 - 1.5 Position; and
 - 1.6 Number of ICT Training Attended?
2. What is the level of ICT competencies of the barangay officials in terms of:
 - 2.1 ICT Basics;
 - 2.2 Word Processing;
 - 2.3 Spreadsheets;
 - 2.4 Presentation;
 - 2.5 Information and Communication; and
 - 2.6 Computer Ethics and Security?
3. Are there significant differences in the level of ICT competencies of the barangay officials when grouped according to their demographic profile?
4. What are the challenges encountered by the barangay officials in using ICT tools?
5. What inputs for a training program may be proposed?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a quantitative research methodology with a sample survey mechanism to gather data on the problem of the study, including the demographic profile of the participants, ICT competency levels, and the challenges encountered in using ICT tools. Moreover, this also determined significant differences in their level of competence in terms of age, gender, highest educational attainment, number of years in service, position, and number of ICT training attended.

The respondents of the study were the incumbent barangay officials from the 32 barangays in the municipality of Prosperidad, Agusan del Sur. The composition of the respondents is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. *Composition of Respondents in the Barangay*

Positions	Composition
Punong Barangay	1
Barangay Kagawad	7
SK Chairman	1
IP Representative	1
Barangay Secretary	1
Barangay Treasurer	1
Barangay Record Keeper	1
Total	13

There are 416 responders in all throughout the 32 barangays. Using Cochran's formula to determine the sample size with a precision level of $\pm 7\%$ and a confidence level of 95%, a minimum sample size of 134 respondents were identified utilizing cluster sampling based on barangay population size. Eleven barangays were randomly selected as samples for the study. However, with the anticipation that not all barangays officials were available during the data gathering or could possibly return the survey questionnaire, the researcher decided to increase the number of barangays to 12, which were randomly selected.

With formal consent from the municipal mayor, the participants were directly reached out in their respective barangay offices using a pen-and-paper survey questionnaire as the primary method for data collection.

The research instrument utilized in this study was adapted from Fuente and Biñas (2020) anchored on the identified basic competency standards of NICS as the framework of this study. It is divided into three sections: (1) Demographic Profile of the Participants, (2) Level of Barangay Officials ICT Competence as shown in Table 2, and (3) Challenges Encountered by the Participants in using ICT tools, as shown in Table 3.

Table 2. *Scoring assigned to the responses on the level of ICT Competencies*

Responses	Numerical Rating	Range	Interpretation
Proficient	5	4.50-5.00	The level of competency is extremely high
Advance	4	3.50-4.49	The level of competency is very high
Intermediate	3	2.50-3.49	The level of competency is average
Basic	2	1.50-2.49	The level of competency is low
Fundamental	1	1.00-1.49	The level of competency is very low

With the identified challenges from the related literature of the study as shown in Table 3, the respondents were asked to check one or more answers or to provide specific answers depending on their assessment.

Table 3. *Challenges Encountered*

Lack of ICT tools or working equipment
Low internet connection
Lack of Knowledge
Lack of Training/s
Others

The data collection process took about a month, starting from the distribution to the collection, due to the availability of the respondents. Additionally, considering the barangays' geographic locations, those in remote areas required more time than expected.

To facilitate statistical analysis, the researcher used frequency and percentage to describe the demographic profile of the participants classified according to age, gender,

highest educational attainment, number of years in service, position, number of trainings attended, and the challenges encountered by the barangay officials in using ICT tools. Mean score, for the level of competencies of the barangay officials based on the area standards by NICS, and test concerning means to determine if significant differences exist in the level of ICT competency when grouped according to age, gender, highest educational attainment, number of years in service, position, and number of ICT training attended.

RESULTS

Demographic Profile of the Participants in terms of:

1. Age;
2. Gender;
3. Highest Educational Attainment;
4. Number of Years in Service;
5. Position;
6. and Number of ICT Training Attended?

The Demographic Profile of the participants is detailed in Table 4.

Table 4. *Frequency and percent distribution of demographic profile of the participants*

Variable	Subgroup	Frequency	Percent
Age	25 years old & below	13	8.39
	26-35 years old	17	10.97
	36-45 years old	41	26.45
	46-55 years old	43	27.74
	56 years old & above	41	26.45
Gender	Female	64	41.29
	Male	91	58.71
Highest Educational Attainment	Bachelor's Degree	32	20.65
	College Level	54	34.84
	Elementary Level	11	7.10
	High School Level	58	37.42
No. of Years in Service	1 year to 3 years	24	15.48
	4 years to 6 years	32	20.65
	7 years and above	42	27.10
	Below 1 year	57	36.77
Position	Barangay Clerk	9	5.81
	Barangay IPMR	10	6.45
	Barangay Kagawad	94	60.65
	Barangay Secretary	12	7.74
	Barangay Treasurer	12	7.74
	Punong Barangay	9	5.81
	SK Chairperson	9	5.81
No. of ICT Trainings Attended	One	3	1.94
	None	137	88.39

In terms of age, participants aged 25 years old and above has the least number with 13 (8.39 %) while those aged 46-55 years old obtained the highest number with 43

(27.74 %). As for gender, 91 (58.71 %) of the participants are male while 64 (41.29 %) are female – indicating that majority of the participants are male. When it comes to the participants' highest educational attainment, the majority are at the high school level with 58 (37.42 %). Grouping the participants by position, 94 (60.65 %) are barangay kagawad. This number is expected because during barangay elections, 7 barangay kagawad are elected. Finally, for the number of ICT trainings attended, a great majority of the participants responded that they did not have any trainings receive related with ICT.

Level of ICT Competencies of the Barangay Officials in terms of:

1. **ICT Basics;**
2. **Word Processing;**
3. **Spreadsheets;**
4. **Presentation;**
5. **Information and Communication; and**
6. **Computer Ethics and Security.**

The level of ICT competencies of the barangay officials based on the six key areas identified in NICS is shown in Table 5.

Table 5. *Level of ICT competencies of the barangay officials*

Item	Mean	Response
ICT Basics		
1. Operate a computer	2.02	Basic
2. Manage files	1.94	Basic
3. Manage a printer	1.91	Basic
4. Arrange and customize the desktop	1.90	Basic
5. Manage applications	1.86	Basic
6. Identify the different hardware and software components of a computer and how they work together	1.85	Basic
7. Explain the terms Information Technology (IT) & Information Communications Technology (ICT)	1.83	Basic
8. Differentiate the different types of software	1.79	Basic
9. Discuss Networking / Communications Technology	1.73	Basic
10. Troubleshoot the computer	1.64	Basic
Average	1.85	Basic
Word Processing		
1. Move, copy, insert, and delete text	2.14	Basic
2. Print a document	2.12	Basic
3. Insert pictures and images	2.10	Basic
4. Insert tables	2.05	Basic
5. Preview a document	2.05	Basic
6. Manage documents	2.02	Basic
7. Format paragraph	2.02	Basic
8. Format document	2.01	Basic
9. Format text	1.96	Basic
Average	2.05	Basic
Spreadsheets		
1. Select cells, Enter data in a cell, Insert and delete cells, and Insert and delete rows and columns	1.99	Basic
2. Preview a worksheet/ Print a worksheet	1.91	Basic

3. Manage workbooks	1.90	Basic
4. Handle worksheets	1.86	Basic
5. Create and format charts/graphs	1.86	Basic
6. Format worksheet	1.84	Basic
7. Format cells	1.83	Basic
8. Format data	1.82	Basic
9. Create formulas and functions	1.79	Basic
Average	2.05	Basic
Presentation		
1. Print slides	1.95	Basic
2. Format text	1.94	Basic
3. Insert pictures and images	1.94	Basic
4. Insert drawn objects	1.94	Basic
5. Create slides/ Use different slide views	1.92	Basic
6. Create a slide show/ Apply slide show effects	1.92	Basic
7. Prepare outputs	1.89	Basic
8. Create charts/graphs	1.88	Basic
9. Discuss basic presentation skills	1.87	Basic
10. Apply slide layouts and templates	1.87	Basic
11. Apply appropriate visuals and design considerations	1.84	Basic
12. Manage presentations using a presentation tool	1.80	Basic
Average	1.90	Basic
Information and Communication		
1. Send and receive email	1.97	Basic
2. Print messages	1.90	Basic
3. Search the Web	1.88	Basic
4. Download web pages	1.83	Basic
5. Access the Web	1.81	Basic
6. Organize messages	1.81	Basic
7. Use Bookmarks	1.79	Basic
8. Discuss Internet and World Wide Web	1.78	Basic
9. Create an Address Book	1.75	Basic
Average	1.84	Basic
Computer Ethics and Security		
1. Understand personal property and user rights	1.87	Basic
2. Apply fundamental principles of computer security	1.81	Basic
3. Understand the concept of software piracy and violation of copyright laws	1.77	Basic
4. Recognize and respond to ethical situations and cyber security issues involving computing devices of all forms	1.77	Basic
5. Recognize examples of copyright violations, computer fraud and possible penalties	1.76	Basic
6. Apply common courtesies and acceptable use policies while telecomputing	1.75	Basic
7. Explain the concept of Security	1.73	Basic
Average	1.78	Basic

Mean: 1.00-1.49-Fundamental, 1.50-2.49- Basic, 2.50-3.49- Intermediate, 3.50-4.49-Advance, 4.50-5.00-Proficient

Overall, the barangay officials possessed a basic level of competency in ICT basics, word processing, spreadsheets, presentation, information and communication,

and computer ethics and security in all six areas evaluated. This suggests that they have an awareness on these concepts and basic knowledge in all these areas.

Significant differences in the level of ICT competencies of the barangay officials when grouped according to their demographic profile

In this section, the study looks into the existence of significant differences in the level of ICT competencies of the barangay officials when grouped according to their demographic profile. Table 6 presents the significant differences in all the six areas.

Table 6. *Significant differences in the level of ICT competencies of the barangay officials in all six areas when grouped according to their demographic profile*

Area	Significant Variables	p-value	Not Significant Variables	p-value
ICT Basics	Age, Gender, Highest Educational Attainment Position	0.000	No. of Years in Service, No. of ICT Trainings Attended	0.079, 0.734
Word Processing	Age, Gender, Highest Educational Attainment Position	0.000	No. of Years in Service, No. of ICT Trainings Attended	0.260, 0.457
Spreadsheets	Age, Gender, Highest Educational Attainment Position	0.000	No. of Years in Service, No. of ICT Trainings Attended	0.113, 0.693
Presentation	Age, Gender, Highest Educational Attainment, Position, No. of Years in Service	0.000, 0.029	No. of ICT Trainings Attended	0.536
Information & Communication	Age, Gender, Highest Educational Attainment, Position	0.000	No. of Years in Service, No. of ICT Trainings Attended	0.260, 0.457
Computer Ethics & Security	Age, Gender, Highest Educational Attainment, Position, No. of Years in Service	0.000, 0.019	No. of ICT Trainings Attended	0.692

As can be noted in the table, there is a significant factor in the level of ICT competency when grouped according to their demographic profile. In ICT basics, word processing, spreadsheets, and information & communication most of the variables were found significant except no. of years in service and no. of ICT trainings attended. Interestingly, in presentation, and computer ethics & security areas, only the no. of ICT trainings was found no significant among all the variables.

Challenges Encountered by the Barangay Officials in Using ICT tools

The respondents were asked to identify the challenges they encountered in using ICT tools, the result is presented in Table 7.

Table 7. Challenges encountered by the barangay officials in using ICT tools

Challenges	Response	Rank
Lack of training/s	58	1
Lack of ICT tools or working equipment	46	2
Lack of knowledge	43	3
Low internet connection	37	4

*Multiple Response

The top challenge encountered by the barangay officials is the lack of training. Though barangay officials may generally have access to various ICT tools, they have not been trained in their usage. Lack of ICT tools or working equipment, lack of knowledge, and low internet connection come next as the challenges faced by the respondents.

Proposed inputs for ICT training program for Barangay Officials

Inclusion of all skill sets in NICS-Basic in the ICT Training. It can be recalled that barangay officials obtained a basic level of competency for each skill set - where an individual has the awareness and basic understanding of the concepts. With this, the training program must include the basic ICT competency standards - ICT Basics, Word Processing, Spreadsheet, Presentation, Information and Communication, and Computer Ethics and Security.

Consideration of the Demographic Profile and the level of ICT competencies in the Design of the Training Program. It has been revealed that most of the variables in the demographics of the respondents have influenced the level of ICT competencies of barangay officials. On this basis, the training program must consider the variations of skills according to their groups.

Provision of ICT tools among Barangays. The availability of the ICT equipment should be prioritized as this is crucial for enhancing the efficiency and effectiveness of the barangay officials. By equipping them with the ICT tools needed in their working environment, these will help them to better manage their daily operations and deliver service to the community. Additionally, regular access to these technologies will further hone their ICT skills.

DISCUSSION

The demographic profile in terms of age reveals that the participants aged 25 years old and above has the least number with 13 (8.39 %) while those who aged 46-55 years old obtained the highest number with 43 (27.74 %). Majority or 91 (58.71 %) of the participants are male while 64 (41.29%) are female – indicating that majority of the participants are male. This finding support what Valente and Moreno (2014) mentioned

that political structures, even at the smallest unit of the government, is a male-dominated arena. When it comes to the respondents' highest educational attainment, the majority are at the high school level with 58 (37.42 %). The data suggest that the majority of the barangay officials have possessed a high school level of education. For the number of years in service, those who have below 1-year experience have the highest frequency with 57 (36.77 %) followed by those whose experience is 1 year to 3 years at 24 (15.48%). This implies that a large percentage of the participants are relatively new in the position. With seven elected barangay kagawad during the election, majority of the respondents are barangay kagawad with 94 (60.65%). A great majority of the participants responded that they did not have any training received related to ICT. However, in the study conducted by Santiago et al (2021) and Bona and Camara (2021), it was recommended that the local government unit should create a program to improve the ICT skills of the barangay officials.

For the level of ICT competence of the barangay officials on the different skill sets in NICS-Basic, they obtained a mean of 1.85 for ICT Basics, 2.05 for Word Processing, 1.87 for Spreadsheets, 1.90 for Presentation, 1.84 for Information and Communication, and 1.78 for Computer Ethics and Security. All these means correspond to a basic level of competency. This result shows the same with the study conducted by Caluza et al (2017) for ICT basics, that most of the teachers only possessed basic knowledge relative to the skills in basic computer operations and other information devices such as troubleshooting, maintenance, and updating offline applications. The result also holds true with the study conducted by Medina et al (2017) on the computer literacy of the barangay council and employees of Mariveles, Bataan, it was found out that the majority of the participants have limited knowledge of operating the three programs such as Word, Powerpoint, and Excel which are usually used in office management. Furthermore, the study of Tapado (2016) among the staff of the government offices in Catanduanes reveals the same result as this, as it showed a 'slightly competent' level of competency when evaluated on the computer literacy skills such as word processing and spreadsheet application, indicating that the employees have limited knowledge and skills. It was also revealed that training to enhance their technology literacy in this area is much needed. On computer ethics and security, as the result showed basic competence, Sourajit (2021) emphasizes that in this digital era with more and more advancements and an increase of cyber security issues, cyber ethics related awareness among common people is of utmost importance. Furthermore, in general, the respondents of this study have awareness and a basic understanding of all six key areas. This level highlights the initial stage of learning ICT concepts and tools and, therefore, the need for foundational training and practice.

Moreover, the study looks into the existence of significant differences in the level of ICT competencies of the barangay officials when grouped according to their demographic profile, such as age, gender, highest educational attainment, and position, while educational attainment and no. of ICT trainings attended were found no significant in most of the areas. One of the factors as presented above was the lack of ICT tools or equipment to use to further hone their skills.

Lack of training emerges as the top challenge encountered among barangay officials. However, in the studies of Santiago et al (2021), Bona and Camara (2021), and Tapado (2016) it was recommended to create an ICT training to enhance the ICT skills.

In providing an ICT training, it is important that all skill sets in NICS-Basic are included – ICT Basics, Word Processing, Spreadsheet, Presentation, Information and Communication, and Computer Ethics and Security as barangay officials have basic level of competency in all these skill sets. The demographic profile of the barangay officials should also be considered in the design of the ICT training. Specifically, this includes the age, gender, highest educational attainment, and position, as these variables are reported to have influenced the level of ICT competencies of the barangay officials for ICT Basics, Word Processing, Spreadsheet, Presentation, Information and Communication, and Computer Ethics and Security.

Conclusions

The demographic profile of the barangay officials in terms of age, gender, highest educational attainment, number of years in service, position, and number of ICT training attended is varied. This variation significantly influences their level of ICT competency. The barangay officials possess a basic level of competency in the different skill sets outlined in NICS-Basic, namely ICT Basics, Word Processing, Spreadsheets, Presentation, Information and Communication, and Computer Ethics and Security. Significant differences exist in the level of competency of the barangay officials when grouped according to their demographic profile.

The lack of training is the top challenge encountered among barangay officials in using ICT tools. This gap in training not only affects their daily operations but also limits their ability to explore and utilize the use of ICT tools.

Given these findings, in providing ICT training for barangay officials, all skill sets in NICS-Basic should be included, and the demographic profile of the barangay officials should be considered.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations have been made:

1. It is recommended that ICT training programs should consider the demographic profile of the barangay officials such as age, gender, highest educational attainment, and position. By analyzing these factors, the facilitators of the training can better understand and address the needs of each group. In addition, the LGU may initiate a mentorship program by establishing partnership between barangays, pairing younger, tech-savvy officials or those with higher educational attainment with older officials or those with less ICT experience. This will provide guidance and support in using ICT tools, helping bridge the ICT skill gap between

generations and foster an environment for inclusiveness and promote a sense of belonging among all officials regardless of age in learning about ICT.

2. It is best that a comprehensive onboarding ICT program may be conducted. This may be done prior to the date the barangay officials will officially assume their posts, to equip them with the essential ICT skills needed to start their day one in service. The training program may cover all the skill sets identified in the NICS-Basic framework through interactive, hands-on activities, including ICT Basics, Word Processing, Spreadsheets, Presentation, Information and Communication, and Computer Ethics and Security.
3. It is ideal for LGU-Prosperidad to establish a partnership and explore opportunities with the Department of Information and Communications Technology (DICT) for the conduct of the ICT training program for barangay officials. This collaboration aims to provide access to training materials, training facilitators, and possible provision of ICT tools to barangays.
4. For equipping skills among barangay officials, the budget allocation for the procurement of ICT tools among the barangays of Prosperidad may be prioritized by the LGU. This may include the provision of the necessary tools such as computers, laptops, printers, and internet connectivity to support daily operations in delivering public service. If budget warrants, purchasing software applications and cybersecurity measures may also be considered.
5. To the future researchers, it is recommended to conduct a comprehensive impact assessment of the onboarding ICT program, the mentorship program, and the use of NICS-Basic framework. This assessment may focus on determining if these programs significantly contribute to enhancing the ICT competencies of barangay officials, improving the delivery of public service, and fostering better governance practices.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors hereby attest that the highest ethical standards were strictly followed during the entire research process of this study. Participants provided informed consent, retained the right to withdraw from the study at any time, and their anonymity was preserved while ensuring their well-being. The study was carried out without any conflicts of interest, plagiarism was strictly avoided, and the results were interpreted objectively. The results were used solely for the purpose of this study.

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